

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Phosphinic, Phenylphosphinic and Phosphorous Acids by Bromine

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Manuscript received 14 February 1991

Oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus by aqueous bromine has been studied in the $[H^+]$ range 0.001–5.0 mol dm⁻³. The reaction is first order with respect to bromine and the oxyacid. Molecular bromine has been postulated as the reactive oxidising species. Oxidation of deuteriated phosphinic and phosphorous acids exhibited substantial kinetic isotope effect. A study of $[H^+]$ variation showed the oxy-anion is oxidised much more rapidly than the parent acid. It is proposed that the 'inactive' tautomer of the oxyacid participates in the oxidation process. A suitable mechanism has been suggested.

Kinetic studies of the reactions of lower oxyacids of phosphorus is of interest because of the existence of two tautomeric forms¹,

1 ; R=H, 2 ; R=Ph, 3 ; R=OH

Generally tautomer (A) is called the 'inactive' form and (B) the 'active' tautomer. The value¹ of K_t is *ca.* 10⁻¹³ for R=H. Kinetics of oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus by transition metal ions have received considerable attention². There are, however, not many reports about their oxidations by halogens³. We report herein kinetics of oxidation of phosphinic (1), phenylphosphinic (2) and phosphorous (3) acids by aqueous bromine.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation of 1 results in the formation of 3. 1 is oxidised at *ca.* three times the rate of oxidation of 3. To reduce the effect of further oxidation of 3 on the kinetics and stoichiometry of oxidation of 1, the [oxyacid] was always kept in large excess over [bromine].

The oxidation exhibited a 1 : 1 stoichiometry (Table 1) and the overall reaction may be written as

Kinetic and other data were obtained for all the three oxyacids. Since the results are similar, only those of 1 are presented here.

TABLE 1—STOICHIOMETRY OF OXIDATION OF PHOSPHOROUS OXYACIDS BY BROMINE

[Br ₂] mol dm ⁻³	[Oxyacid] mol dm ⁻³	[Product] mol dm ⁻³	[Product]/ [Br ₂]
Phosphinic acid			
0.020	0.50	0.021	1.05
0.040	0.50	0.044	1.10
0.050	0.50	0.056	1.12
Mean = 1.09 ± 0.03			
Phenylphosphinic acid			
0.020	0.50	0.022	1.10
0.050	0.50	0.057	1.14
0.080	0.50	0.080	1.00
Mean = 1.08 ± 0.06			
Phosphorous acid			
[Br ₂] mol dm ⁻³	[Oxyacid] mol dm ⁻³	[Residual Br ₂] mol dm ⁻³	$\frac{\Delta[\text{Br}_2]}{\Delta[\text{Oxyacid}]}$
0.300	0.05	0.246	1.01
0.300	0.07	0.228	1.03
0.300	0.10	0.202	0.98
Mean = 1.03 ± 0.05			

TABLE 2 - RATE CONSTANTS OF OXIDATION OF PHOSPHINIC ACID BY BROMINE

$[H^+] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 298 K

10 ³ [Br ₂] mol dm ⁻³	[1] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k _{obs} s ⁻¹
1.0	0.3	1.47
2.0	0.3	1.42
4.0	0.3	1.45
6.0	0.3	1.38
8.0	0.3	1.40
10.0	0.3	1.46
2.0	0.2	0.95
2.0	0.4	1.90
2.0	0.6	2.86
2.0	0.8	3.71
2.0	1.0	4.66

The reaction rate follows equation (3) at constant $[H^+]$ (Table 2).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 [\text{oxyacid}] [\text{oxidant}] \quad (3)$$

In aqueous media Br_2 exists with HOBr and Br_3^- . If all these are kinetically significant then

$$k_2 = k_{Br_2} K_3 / (K_3 + [Br_3^-]) + K_{Br_2} [Br^-] / (K_3 + [Br^-]) + K_{HOBr} K_3 K_h / (K_3 + [Br^-]) [H^+] \quad (4)$$

where K_3 is the dissociation constant of Br_3^- to Br_2 and Br^- , K_h is the hydrolysis constant of bromine, and use is made of the fact that under our experimental conditions,

$$[HOBr] \ll [Bromine] \quad (5)$$

The oxidation was studied at different concentrations of bromide ion (Table 3). A plot of k_2

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF BROMIDE ION ON OXIDATION OF 1 BY BROMINE

$[Br_2]=0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[I] 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp.=298 K

$[Br^-]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	0.02	0.04	0.08	0.12	0.16	0.20	0.25
$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	3.50	2.71	2.00	1.43	1.20	1.03	0.87

against $1/(K_3 + [Br^-])$ at constant $[H^+]$ is a straight line passing through the origin ($r, 0.9992$, intercept, $-1.69 \pm 3.8 \times 10^{-6}$; slope, $2.67 \pm 0.05 \times 10^{-6}$). Values of K_3 were obtained from the literature⁴. The fact that a straight line is obtained, led us to conclude that in these reactions Br_3^- and HOBr are kinetically insignificant compared to molecular bromine, and equation (4) reduces to equation (6),

$$k_2 = k_{Br_2} K_3 / (K_3 + [Br^-]) \quad (6)$$

The values of k_{Br_2} were calculated from the slopes of plots of k_2 against $1/(K_3 + [Br^-])$, which are equal to $K_3 k_{Br_2}$.

Oxidation by hypobromous acid: Results of the previous section gave no information about k_{HOBr} . We, therefore, studied the oxidation by hypobromous acid. Plots of $\log [\text{oxidant}]$ against time revealed an autocatalytic process. This may be because of the reduction of HOBr to bromide ion which reacted with unchanged HOBr to give bromine which in turn attacked the phosphorus compound. The reaction was, therefore, carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm^{-3} mercury(II) nitrate to scavenge bromide ion⁵. The results (Table 4) show that in fact $k_{HOBr} \ll k_{Br_2}$. The ratio k_{Br_2}/k_{HOBr} increases as the $[H^+]$ decreases.

Effect of acidity: The oxidation by bromine was studied in the $[H^+]$ range $5.0-0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 5). Two series of experiments were carried out. The first in the presence of 0.2 mol dm^{-3} of bromide ions and the second in the absence of any added bromide ion. It is seen that in both

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS OF OXIDATION OF PHOSPHINIC ACID BY HYPOBROMOUS ACID AT 298 K

$[H^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	5.0	2.0	0.5
$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	1.35	2.32	4.11
k_{Br_2}/k_{HOBr}	27.0	35.8	78.3

the series, rate decreases sigmoidally as acidity increases. The results resemble the ionisation curve of a weak acid.

It is proposed that the increase in rate with a decrease in hydrogen ion concentration is due to the superior kinetic activity of the oxo-anion than the parent oxyacid. The rate constant is thus composite (equation 7),

$$k_{Br_2} = k_{\text{oxyacid}} + k_{\text{anion}} K_a / (K_a + [H^+]) \quad (7)$$

where K_a is the dissociation constant of the oxyacid. The values of K_a were obtained from the literature⁶.

The values of k_{oxyacid} and k_{anion} were evaluated at four different temperatures, and activation parameters were calculated (Table 6).

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION ON REACTION RATE

$[I]=0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Br_2]=0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp.=298 K

$[H^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	
	$[Br^-]$ 0.0 mol dm ⁻³	$[Br^-]$ 0.2 mol dm ⁻³
5.0	3.65	0.80
4.0	3.82	0.84
3.5	3.95	0.86
3.0	4.13	0.90
2.5	4.38	0.96
2.0	4.72	1.03
1.5	5.30	1.16
1.0	6.45	1.41
0.70	7.70	1.68
0.50	9.43	2.06
0.20	16.5	3.60
0.10	24.1	5.27
0.05	32.2	7.04
0.02	41.1	9.00
0.01	45.3	9.91
0.005	47.9	10.5
0.002	49.7	10.9
0.001	50.1	11.0

In several oxidations by bromine⁷ the observed increase in the reaction rate with a decrease in hydrogen ion concentration has been interpreted in terms of equation (8) assuming that hypobromous acid is the more reactive species,

However, our results show that this hypothesis is untenable. First, the oxidation by bromine-free hypobromous acid was extremely slow. Secondly, the increase in rate with decreasing hydrogen ion concentration is most pronounced when the formation of hypobromous acid is suppressed by the addition of an excess of bromide ion. The results

TABLE 6—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Acid	Rate constants at				$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ m l ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
	10 ³ k_{anion} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)						
1	3.72	7.73	14.1	25.5	46.1 ± 0.6	-113 ± 2	79.4 ± 0.5
2	10.5	20.5	39.7	75.5	47.6 ± 0.5	-99 ± 2	76.9 ± 0.4
3	1.12	2.18	4.35	8.62	49.3 ± 0.9	-112 ± 3	82.4 ± 0.7
	10 ³ k_{oxyacid} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)						
1	2.07	4.43	9.05	18.7	53.2 ± 0.6	-112 ± 2	86.4 ± 0.4
2	7.72	15.5	28.8	56.5	47.6 ± 0.7	-120 ± 2	83.4 ± 0.5
3	0.71	1.39	2.79	5.52	49.6 ± 0.8	-134 ± 3	89.2 ± 0.7

support the view that the increase in the rate can be attributed to the relatively rapid oxidation of the anion of the oxyacid. Similar conclusions were reached earlier in the oxidation of glucose⁸, hydroxy acids⁹ and 2-propanol¹⁰.

Kinetic isotope effect: The oxidation of deuterated 1 and 3 exhibited substantial primary kinetic isotope effects ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}=4.52$ and 4.73 respectively at 298 K). This confirms that a P-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step.

Mechanism: Lower oxyacids of phosphorus are reported to exhibit tautomerism¹, and the 'active' form is postulated as an intermediate in the acid-catalysed exchange of phosphorous-bonded hydrogen with deuterium and tritium. Two alternate mechanisms can thus be postulated. In one the 'inactive' form is assumed to be reactive species (equations 8 and 9).

The rate law governing the sequence of reactions (1), (9) and (10) has the following form, acknowledging that $K_1 \ll 1$,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = [\text{Br}_2] \left\{ k_{2a} [\text{oxyacid}] + \frac{K_1 k_{2a'} [\text{anion}]}{K_1 + [\text{H}^+]} \right\} \quad (11)$$

Similarly an alternate mechanism is proposed for the oxidation of the 'active' form of the oxyacid (equations 12 and 13) which leads to the rate law (14), again acknowledging that $1 \gg K_1$,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = [\text{Br}_2] \left\{ K_1 k_{2b} [\text{oxyacid}] + \frac{K_1 K_1 k_{2b'} [\text{anion}]}{K_1 + [\text{H}^+]} \right\} \quad (14)$$

Thus the two rate laws are experimentally indistinguishable and confirms to the observed law.

If reactions (12) and (13) represent the mechanism of the oxidation, then the specific rate constants k_{oxyacid} and k_{anion} are given by equation (15),

$$k_{\text{oxyacid}} = K_1 k_{2b}; k_{\text{anion}} = K_1 K_1 k_{2b'} \quad (15)$$

The value of K_1 is of the order of 10^{-12} and that of K_2 is of 10^{-2} . Therefore, the values of rate-limiting constants, k_{2b} and $k_{2b'}$, come between 10^{12} and 10^{15} dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹. These rate constants exceed/equal the rate constants of diffusion-controlled processes¹¹. Therefore, one can rule out the participation of the 'active' tautomer of the phosphorous oxyacid in the oxidation process.

The presence of substantial primary kinetic isotope effect confirms the rupture of a P-H bond in the rate-determining step. There is no kinetic evidence for the formation of an intermediate. The large kinetic isotope effect points against a non-linear transition state implied in an ester mechanism. Hence, it is proposed that the rate-determining step involves a hydride ion transfer to the oxidant. Such a reaction can be easily imagined to be facilitated by the presence of a negative charge on the reductant molecule.

Experimental

The phosphorus oxyacids (Fluka) and bromine (Merck) were commercial products and used as such. Aqueous solutions of the oxyacids were standardised

by alkalimetry. Perchloric acid and acetate buffer were used to maintain the hydrogen ion concentration. Hypobromous acid solutions were prepared by mixing yellow mercuric oxide and bromine water and distilling under reduced pressure in an all-glass apparatus¹².

The P-H bonds in 1 and 3 were deuteriated by dissolving the acid in deuterium oxide (B.A.R.C. ; 99.4 % purity) and evaporating the excess of deuterium oxide and water under reduced pressure¹³. The isotropic purity of deuteriated 1 and 3, as determined by their nmr spectra, were 91 ± 5 and $93 \pm 4\%$ respectively.

Stoichiometry : The oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus by bromine leads to the formation of the corresponding higher oxyacids of phosphorus. Reaction mixtures, containing a known excess of 1 or 2, were prepared. After completion of the reaction, phosphorous and phenylphosphonic acid formed were determined by the reported method¹⁴. To determine the stoichiometry of the oxidation of 3, the reaction mixtures containing a known excess of bromine were prepared and after completion of the reaction, the residual bromine was determined iodometrically.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess of the oxyacid over bromine. The reaction was followed iodometrically. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was evaluated from the linear least-squares plot of $\log [\text{oxidant}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$. The second order rate constant (k_2) was obtained from the relationship $k_2 = k_{obs}/[\text{oxyacid}]$. Preliminary experiments showed that the reactions are not sensitive to ionic strength, hence no attempt was made to keep the ionic strength constant.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial support.

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